

Preparation of Wood/Montmorillonite(MMT) Intercalation Nanocomposite

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Abstract The analysis of Chinese fir wood impregnating treatment shows that the impregnating effect of WMNC is related to the factors, such as MMT content, impregnating time and temperature, impregnating pressure, wood moisture content and wood extracting treatment and so on. The analysis results of XRD of WMNC indicated that some MMT layers were exfoliated in wood and combined with wood in nano sizes. FTIR analysis indicated hydrogen bonds or some chemical linkages were produced between MMT and wood in WMNC. By comparing the TG-DTA analysis of WMNC with PF impregnating wood, it can be deduced that a certain nano effect produced in WMNC.

Keyword: wood/montmorillonite nanocomposite, preparation, properties

1 Introduction

In order to impart better mechanical properties to plantation timber such as abrasion resistance, surface hardness, fire resistance, decay resistance and so on, intercalation method was used to prepare wood/montmorillonite nanocomposite(WMNC) with PF resin as intermediate in this research. In this paper, we focus on several factors in the process of preparing WMNC such as concentration of PF resin, MMT content, impregnating temperature and time and so on.

From the figure 1, we know that: on the basis of the dispersion state of silicate layers in wood matrix, WMNC can be classified into three groups: 1)Traditional form(figure Ia, IIa): the particles of MMT disperse homogeneously in water-soluble PF resin of which no macromolecules enter the silicate layers. The interlayer distance has no change and particles of MMT will exist in macro pores of wood, cell cavity for instance. 2) Intercalated form(figure Ib, IIb): the macromolecules of water-soluble PF resin enter the silicate layers and make them swell in a certain degree, which make the interlayer distance enlarged. Whereas, the silicate layers are still highly ordered for the existence of van der Waals forces. The layers of this type of MMT will partly come into wood cell wall, and partly stay in the holes like wood cell cavity. 3) Exfoliation form(figure Ic, IIc): MMT enter wood cell wall directly and bond with hydrogen bonds and part of chemical bonds of wood in molecules level.

Fig.1. Type of intercalated nanocomposites

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Organophilic montmorillonite(OMMT) was prepared using a kind of alkyl ammonium salt. Low molecular weight water-soluble PF resin. Chinese fir(*Cunninghamia lanceolata*) has an air-dry density of 0.365g/cm³ and moisture content of about 9%.The sample's size varies from experiments.

2.2 Preparation of wood/MMT nanocomposite(WMNC)

The synthesized low molecular weight water-soluble PF resin was added to some water to get certain concentration, then a certain ratio OMMT was put into the solution. The resulting solution was the impregnant which was impregnated into wood samples under vacuum. Then the samples were air dried and cured at certain temperature and time.

Fig.2. Schematic processes to prepare wood/MMT nanocomposites

As showed as figure2, The process of preparation technique can be classified into one-step process and two-step process. One-step process means that intercalation compounding of intermediate and MMT is

simultaneous with wood impregnation. OMMT suspension is mixed with a certain water-soluble polymer solution. During the process of the polymer entering into OMMT with water, OMMT is impregnated into nano space of wood cell walls or macro space of wood cell cavities. Two-step process is to impregnate OMMT solution into wood after the intermediate has intercalated into OMMT. First OMMT suspension is mixed with a certain water-soluble polymer solution. After polymer with water as intermediate has intercalated into layers of OMMT to get nano composite, the composite is impregnated into wood.

2.3 The characterization of WMNC using XRD , FTIR, TG-DTA

X-ray analysis: X-ray diffractometer (SHIMADZU, XRD-6000) uses Cu K α radiation (40kv,30mA, $\lambda=0.154\text{nm}$) in a range of $2\theta=1.5\sim 40^\circ$ with a scanning rate of $4^\circ/\text{min}$. Each interval is 0.01° .

FTIR analysis: The FTIR spectra were recorded on a German Tensor27 Infrared Spectrophotometer using KBr disc with a scanning range of $400\text{cm}^{-1}\sim 4000\text{cm}^{-1}$.

TG-DTA analysis: TG-DTA analyses were carried out under air on a SHIMADZU DT-60 analyzer, using a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, from room temperature to 600°C . The air velocity is $100\text{ml}/\text{min}$, and the sample's quantity is $6\sim 9\text{mg}$.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Wood impregnating treatment and analysis

3.1.1 Effect of MMT content

Fig. 3. Effect of MMT content on weight percent gain (WPG) of WMNC

From the figure 3, it can be seen that WPG of sap wood increases with an increase of MMT content. However, WPG of heart wood not only has increase, but also has decrease.

Fig.4 Effect of MMT content on swelling coefficient of WMNCAs

Showed as figure 4, from the beginning, swelling coefficient increases with MMT content increase. Then there is a turning point, it decreases when MMT content increases. MMT content corresponding to the highest swelling coefficient of sapwood is 3%, corresponding to that of heartwood is 5%.

3.1.2 Effect of impregnating temperature

Fig.5. Effect of impregnating temperature on weight percent gain (WPG) of WMNC

As showed as figure5, when the temperature is between 20°C~80°C, WPG has a little increase with an increase of temperature. And it has an abrupt increase when the temperature is above 80°C.

3.1.3 Effect of impregnating pressure

Fig.6. Effect of impregnating pressure on weight percent gain of WMNCAs

Showed as figure6, With impregnating pressure increasing, wood WPG has a big increase where WPG of heart wood has a bigger increase than that of sap wood.

3.1.4 Influence of wood extraction treatment

Fig.7 Effect of wood extracting treatment on weight percent gain (WPG) of WMNC

We can see from the figure7 that WPG of wood treated with several kinds of extraction are all greater than that of untreated wood in spite of sap wood and heart wood which shows that extractives have a great influence on wood penetrability.

3.1.5 Influence of wood moisture content

Fig.8 Effect of wood moisture content on weight percent gain (WPG) of WMNC

From the figure8, the impregnation WPG of air-dried wood is the biggest. But the WPG of air-dried wood is almost the same with that of oven-dry wood for sap wood.

3.2 XRD analysis

Fig.9. XRD analysis of Wood/MMT intercalation Nanocomposite

In Fig.9, a, b and c represent XRD patterns of PF/wood powder, a blend powder of PF/wood and OMMT and WMNC powder respectively. It can be seen from a that there are two broad peaks around $2\theta=15.41^\circ$ and $2\theta=21.93^\circ$ and a small peak around $2\theta=37.75^\circ$. The diffraction peak around $2\theta=21.93^\circ$ is the maximum peak of cellulose 002 crystal plane. The diffraction trough around $2\theta=18^\circ$ reflects amorphous region. The small peak

around $2\theta=37.75^\circ$ is the diffraction of cellulose 040 crystal plane. In b, the distinctive peak of OMMT can be obviously seen. The silicate layers distance remains constant. Fig.1(c) is XRD patterns of WMNC with the same quality ratio. The disappearance of XRD peak ($2\theta=3.38^\circ$) in original OMMT indicates that these silicate layers distance in WMNC is further enlarged, or the layers could even be exfoliated. Compared with that of Fig.1(a), in Fig.1(c), the diffraction around $2\theta=16\sim 18^\circ$ increases. The diffraction trough of PF impregnated wood becomes flat and there comes a small and sharp peak around $2\theta=17^\circ$. The peaks of cellulose 002 crystal plane around $2\theta=15.41^\circ$ and $2\theta=21.93^\circ$ becomes blunt and the small diffraction peaks of cellulose 040 crystal plane around $2\theta=37.75^\circ$ almost disappear. Thus it can be seen that when wood combines with MMT to get wood/MMT nanocomposite, the layers are partially exfoliated and infiltrate into the matrix of wood cell wall.

3.3 FTIR analysis

Fig.10 FTIR spectra of WMNC and (Chinese fir wood)

Fig.11 FTIR spectra of WMNC and PF/Wood composites (Chinese fir wood)

From the figure 10 and 11, it can be seen that absorption spectrum belt of $3200\text{cm}^{-1}\sim 3500\text{cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to hydroxyl vibration is broader obviously, but the absorption intensity declines. It can be concluded that dissociated hydroxyl of composite decreases and associated hydroxyl of composite increases. And new linkage may come into being by oxygen among components of composite.

Fig.12 FTIR subtraction spectrum of WMNC and PF/Wood composites Figure 12 is FTIR subtraction spectrum analysis. The result shows that the absorption peak intensity around 3300cm^{-1} 、 1595cm^{-1} and

$1060\text{cm}^{-1}\sim 1300\text{cm}^{-1}$ increases and there are big absorption peaks around 1042cm^{-1} 、 464cm^{-1} and so on. It is analyzed that associated hydroxyl and ether bond of WMNC enhances which account for MMT and wood of nanocomposite bonding with hydrogen bond and other chemical linkage.

3.4 TG-DTA analysis.

Fig.13 TG-DTA analysis of PF/Wood and WMNC(Chinese fir wood, O₂ atmosphere)

As showed as figure 13, there are about five peaks of PF impreg DTA curve which can be divided into five pyrogenation steps. WMNC DTA curve has four peaks which divided into four steps. The peak and peak temperature of second and third step of WMNC in pyrogenation are almost the same with that of PF impreg, but its exotherm peak is bigger and the temperature of its biggest exotherm peak is a bit higher. In the fourth step, its exotherm peak decreases markedly. After that, the decomposing rate slows down. Above 450°C, DTA curve of PF impreg is markedly higher than that of WMNC. From these different decomposition, it can be concluded that there exists a certain nano effect in WMNC composite.

4 Conclusions

The analysis of Chinese fir wood impregnating treatment shows that the impregnating effect of WMNC is related to the factors, such as MMT content, impregnating time and temperature, impregnating pressure, wood moisture content and wood extracting treatment and so on.

The analysis results of XRD of WMNC indicated that some MMT layers were exfoliated in wood and combined with wood in nano sizes.

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LITERATURE

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